

A STUDY ON DISPARITIES IN HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX IN MANDYA DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT:

The Human Development Index (HDI) measures each country's social and economic development by focusing on the following four factors: mean years of schooling, expected years of schooling, life expectancy at birth, and gross national income (GNI) per capita. The Human Development Index (HDI) is a tool that measures and compares the development and well-being of countries. It is used to help policymakers and organizations make informed decisions. The HDI is considered effective in measuring a country's performance in terms of socio-economic factors. It is also an essential indicator of a nation's overall socio-economic conditions and its residents. This paper explores the intra-taluk disparities in Human Development Index (HDI) in Mandya District in Karnataka. This study shows that Mandya district in Karnataka has a Human Development Index (HDI) of 0.644 in 2022-23. Mandya district has a total of seven taluks and when comparing the human development index of seven taluks, it can be seen that there is a difference in them. Mandya taluk ranked first with HDI values of 0.6979 in the year 2019 among various taluks of Mandya district. And Krishnarajpet was ranked 7th with HDI values of 0.5942, Maddur was ranked 2nd with HDI values of 0.6382, Pandavapura was ranked 3rd with HDI values of 0.6292, Srirangapatna taluk was ranked 4th with HDI values of 0.6164, Malavalli was ranked 5th with HDI values of 0.6081, Nagamangala was ranked 3rd with HDI values of 0.5961. 6th position. If you look at the human development index of Mandya district, the human development index of people living in urban areas is higher as compared to the people of rural areas, because they have health, education and sources of income in a better condition compared to the people of rural areas. It can be observed that the human development index of all the taluks of Mandya district is better in 2019 as compared to 2011. Besides, it can be observed in the above list that there has been improvement in health education and quality of life.

Keywords: Human Development Index (HDI), Disparities, Socio-economic Development.

INTRODUCTION

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a statistical index that measures a country's average achievements in three areas of human development: health, knowledge, and standard of living, it is developed by Mahbub Ul Haq, a Pakistani economist and Indian Nobel laureate Amartya Sen in 1991. It was later adopted by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) for measuring the development of countries. Since that milestone, annual reports have been consistently published, delving into various themes using the human development approach, which prioritizes placing individuals at the core of the development process.

The Human Development Report is published by the Human Development Report Office (HDRO) of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) since 1990. It is an annual Human Development report. The latest Human Development Report 2021-2022, published on September 8, 2022, calculates HDI values based on data collected in 2021. India ranked 132 out of 191 countries in the latest human development index, with an HDI value of 0.633, which was lower than the global average of 0.732.

COMPONENTS OF HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX

The following are the components of Human Development Index.

1. **Health:** The first component of HDI is health and for determining a long and healthy life, life expectancy is the most important parameter.
2. **Education:** The development of a nation can be indicated by another important component which is education. Education can be measured in two stages, which can be as expected years of schooling that is based on entry level schooling age and mean years of schooling (total schooling age) for the adult population.
3. **Income:** The third parameter that is considered for determining a good standard of living is income and it is determined by the gross national income per capita.

The HDI is calculated as follows:

- ❖ Original HDI: $\frac{1}{3}(\text{Life Expectancy}) + \frac{1}{3}(\text{Education}) + \frac{1}{3}(\text{Per-Capita Income})$
- ❖ Hybrid HDI: Uses geometric mean instead of arithmetic mean

The HDI is a classification system that categorizes human development into four groups:

- ❖ Low human development: HDI less than 0.550
- ❖ Medium human development: HDI 0.550–0.699
- ❖ High human development: HDI 0.700–0.799
- ❖ Very high human development: HDI 0.800 or greater

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. Basavaraj S. Benni and others (2017) “Disparities in Human Development of Hyderabad Karnataka Region” in this paper analyses the disparities in human development of Hyderabad Karnataka region and compares human development indices for various taluk’s of this region. To analyse results, researchers were used simple statistical tools like percentage, average, Coefficient of Variation etc. The study found that still there are more variations in taluk human development in Hyderabad Karnataka Region. the inter-taluk disparities in human development were analysed. Balanced regional development has been one of the prime objectives of the any government. The existence of the backward regions in developing countries like ours necessitates supplementary emphasis on balanced regional development. In 2008 onwards Government of Karnataka had releases special grants to HK region, but it is noticed that in HK region there are variations in the taluk level Disparities in human development index. Government has to take steps to increase human development facilities in the villages, such as health and education, and develop appropriate infrastructure such as

roads and communication, there is the requirement for creation employment, which can improve the living conditions and need to adopt a long-term policy. Hence the human development improved in this region.

Niranjan. R and others (2021) “Regional Inequality in Human Development in Karnataka: A Spatial Analysis” in this paper analyses the trend and pattern of inequality in human development across districts of Karnataka. To gauge the extent of spatial inequalities at sub-regional level, the study makes use of the district wise HDI data drawn from Karnataka, District Human Development Reports (1991, 2001 and 2014). The spatial inequality in human development and its components are evaluated by using Moran’s Inequality index, LISA cluster map and LISA significant maps. The study finds that the overall spatial inequality in human development has declined. However, the spatial concentration in HDI has seen an increasing trend in Karnataka. It is observed that the districts of northern Karnataka, particularly the Hyderabad-Karnataka region have low levels of human development. Improved access and services of health, education and other deprivations at micro levels reduced spatial inequality and improved human development in the state.

RESEARCH GAP

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable and having a decent standard of living. The HDI is the geometric mean of normalized indices for each of the three dimensions. It is necessary to determine social measures of development for calculating the overall development of a nation. Human Development Index measures the socio-economic factors and therefore, is considered very effective in measuring the performance of a country in terms of these factors. There are a good number of studies, explaining Role and performance Human development index and disparities in human development in India. The literature survey revealed some of the study was related to trends of human development index, role of HDI in measure socio-economic development of Indian economy there are only few studies focused on disparities in human development in Karnataka as well as Manday District. Thus, the review of literature clearly shows that there is dearth of studies relating to Disparities in Human development index in Mandya District in Karnataka. Hence the present study makes an attempt to explore Disparities in Human development index in Mandya District in Karnataka and also analyse trends in Human development index in India and Karnataka.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the trends of Human development Index in India and Karnataka.
2. To explore the Disparities in Human development index in Mandya District in Karnataka.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is statistically significant difference in Disparities in Human development index in across the taluks of Mandya District in Karnataka in 2019.

Methodology of the Study

The present study is on empirical investigation purely based on secondary data. Secondary data collected from Various Books, Newspapers, journals, Human Development reports of India and Karnataka and UNDP website. So, the quality of study depends upon accuracy, reliability and quality of that data. After collection of data, these are arranged in tabular format. The analysis was done by using different statistical tools and the analysed data are

presented in tabulated form. The data is analysed by using the Simple tables, Charts, percentage method is used to analyses the data, and Chi-square test used to Hypothesis.

HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX IN INDIA

The HDR was titled as ‘‘Uncertain Times, Unsettled Lives: Shaping our Future in a Transforming World’’. The Special report disclosed for 2022 had been titled ‘New Threats to Human Society in the Anthropocene’ and expressed that the feeling of security and safety is at a minimum in the majority of the countries, counting in the richest countries in spite of their surged level of success. India is now one of the fastest-growing economies globally. However, this growth has not resulted in a corresponding increase in its Human Development Index (HDI). The HDI is a composite statistical measure created by the United Nations Development Programme to evaluate and compare the level of human development in different regions around the world. It was introduced in 1990 as an alternative to conventional economic measures such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which do not consider the broader aspects of human development. The HDI assesses a country’s average accomplishment in three aspects: a long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of living. However, this growth has not resulted in a corresponding increase in its Human Development Index (HDI). According to the Human Development Report of 2021-22, India ranks 132 out of 191 countries, behind Bangladesh (129) and Sri Lanka (73).

Table 1: Human Development Index across the States of India in 2022

Sl.No	States	Health index	Educational index	Income index	HDI index	Rank
1.	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	0.82	0.607	0.706	0.706	7
2.	Andhra Pradesh	0.734	0.517	0.66	0.63	26
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	0.767	0.575	0.665	0.665	20
4.	Assam	0.714	0.53	0.564	0.597	31
5.	Bihar	0.712	0.48	0.544	0.571	36
6.	Chandigarh	0.78	0.704	0.751	0.744	3
7.	Chhattisgarh	0.689	0.528	0.609	0.605	30
8.	Dadra and Nagar Haveli	0.766	0.507	0.613	0.62	29
9.	Daman and Diu	0.772	0.554	0.675	0.661	21
10.	Goa	0.809	0.696	0.752	0.751	2
11.	Gujarat	0.745	0.519	0.669	0.638	24
12.	Haryana	0.756	0.613	0.713	0.691	12
13.	Himachal Pradesh	0.757	0.649	0.709	0.703	8
14.	Jammu and Kashmir	0.762	0.644	0.696	0.699	10
15.	Jharkhand	0.715	0.512	0.557	0.589	35
16.	Karnataka	0.777	0.567	0.673	0.667	19
17.	Kerala	0.834	0.713	0.716	0.752	1
18.	Lakshadweep	0.785	0.649	0.718	0.715	6
19.	Madhya Pradesh	0.693	0.509	0.6	0.596	33
20.	Maharashtra	0.779	0.62	0.676	0.688	13
21.	Manipur	0.783	0.656	0.606	0.678	16
22.	Meghalaya	0.753	0.572	0.616	0.643	23
23.	Mizoram	0.725	0.636	0.705	0.688	14
24.	Nagaland	0.767	0.614	0.639	0.67	18

25.	New Delhi	0.775	0.684	0.733	0.73	4
26.	Orissa	0.717	0.505	0.587	0.597	32
27.	Puducherry	0.794	0.664	0.724	0.726	5
28.	Punjab	0.765	0.598	0.729	0.694	11
29.	Rajasthan	0.725	0.543	0.66	0.638	25
30.	Sikkim	0.785	0.644	0.683	0.702	9
31.	Tamil Nadu	0.791	0.608	0.671	0.686	15
32.	Telangana	0.748	0.542	0.667	0.647	22
33.	Tripura	0.773	0.549	0.586	0.629	27
34.	Uttar Pradesh	0.667	0.524	0.591	0.592	34
35.	Uttarakhand	0.733	0.609	0.678	0.672	17
36.	West Bengal	0.761	0.534	0.598	0.624	28
India Total		0.727	0.552	0.633	0.633	

Source: India human Development Repest 2021

Table no 1 show that Human Development Index across the States of India in 2022 According to the Human Development Report of 2021-22 The five States with the highest HDI scores are Delhi, Goa, Kerala, Sikkim, and Chandigarh. The bottom five States are Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand, and Assam, with medium levels of human development. Despite having the highest SGDP per capita among larger States, Gujarat and Haryana have failed to translate this advantage into human development and rank 21 and 10, respectively

- ❖ Human Development Index: India's HDI value stood at 0.633 in 2021, which was lower than the world average of 0.732. In 2020, too, India recorded a decline in its HDI value (0.642) in comparison to the pre-Covid level of 2019 (0.645).
- ❖ Life expectancy: In 2021, India's life expectancy at birth was recorded at 67.2 years.
- ❖ Schooling: Expected years of schooling at 11.9 years, mean years of schooling at 6.7 years,
- ❖ Gross National Income: The gross national income per capita stood at USD 6,590.
- ❖ Gender Inequality Index: India has been ranked 122 on the Gender Inequality Index.

Table 2: Trends of Human Development Index of India from 2002 to 2021

Sl. No	Year	Index	Rank among Countries
1.	2002	0.503	131
2.	2003	0.516	130
3.	2004	0.525	131
4.	2005	0.534	137
5.	2006	0.543	137
6.	2007	0.553	137
7.	2008	0.560	138
8.	2009	0.565	138
9.	2010	0.575	138
10.	2011	0.588	137
11.	2012	0.598	135

12.	2013	0.607	133
13.	2014	0.619	133
14.	2015	0.629	130
15.	2016	0.639	127
16.	2017	0.644	128
17.	2018	0.645	129
18.	2019	0.645	129
19.	2020	0.642	130
20.	2021	0.633	132

Source: <https://countryeconomy.com/hdi/india>

Table no 2 and chart 1 show that Trends of Human Development Index of India from 2002 to 2021. The Human Development Report is published by the Human Development Report Office (HDRO) of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) since 1990. It is an annual Human Development report. The latest Human Development Report 2021-2022, published on September 8, 2022, calculates HDI values based on data collected in 2021. The Human Development Report 2021-22, brought out by the United Nations Development Programme, shows that India's global rankings have gone down from 130 in 2020 to 132 in 2021 out of 191 countries in the latest human development index, with an HDI value of 0.633, which was lower than the global average of 0.732. Based on consistent indicators, methodology and time-series data, India's HDI values were 0.503 in 2002, 0.516 in 2003, 0.534 in 2005, 0.575 in 2010, 0.629 in 2015, 0.645 in 2018, 0.645 in 2019, 0.642 in 2020 and 0.633 in 2021. This is not surprising as the growth in India's Human Development Index (HDI) values have decelerated faster than the global values during the pandemic. India's HDI values, which were stagnant in 2019, fell marginally in 2020—the first year of the pandemic and the fall accelerated almost threefold to -1.4% in 2021. However, at the global level, the fall in HDI indicators was stemmed in 2021 at 0.4%, which is marginally lower than in 2020.

Table 3: Human Development Index across the districts of Karnataka in 2022

Sl.No	Districts	Health Index	Education Index	Income Index	HDI	Rank
1.	Bengaluru	0.770	0.678	0.770	0.738	1

	Urban					
2.	Dakshina Kannada	0.757	0.595	0.720	0.687	2
3.	Chikkamaga luru	0.770	0.576	0.672	0.668	3
4.	Udupi	0.760	0.566	0.684	0.665	4
5.	Kodagu	0.768	0.619	0.616	0.664	5
6.	Mandya	0.764	0.575	0.607	0.644	6
7.	Bengaluru Rural	0.762	0.557	0.625	0.643	7
8.	Ramanagar	0.761	0.565	0.615	0.642	8
9.	Kolar	0.771	0.599	0.567	0.640	9
10.	Shimoga	0.755	0.547	0.623	0.636	10
11.	Uttara Kannada	0.775	0.556	0.586	0.632	11
12.	Bagalkot	0.774	0.542	0.594	0.629	12
13.	Chikkaballap ur	0.768	0.577	0.558	0.628	13
14.	Mysore	0.759	0.557	0.577	0.625	14
15.	Hassan	0.769	0.528	0.598	0.624	15
16.	Gadag	0.767	0.563	0.559	0.623	16
17.	Tumkur	0.759	0.506	0.606	0.615	17
18.	Bellary	0.730	0.523	0.601	0.612	18
19.	Dharwad	0.708	0.533	0.601	0.610	19
20.	Belgaum	0.751	0.546	0.529	0.601	20
21.	Chamarajana gar	0.776	0.488	0.573	0.601	21
22.	Bidar	0.772	0.532	0.527	0.600	22
23.	Vijayapura	0.771	0.524	0.532	0.599	23
24.	Chitradurga	0.757	0.519	0.541	0.597	24
25.	Koppal	0.765	0.520	0.524	0.593	25
26.	Davangere	0.749	0.508	0.538	0.589	26
27.	Haveri	0.762	0.446	0.533	0.566	27
28.	Raichur	0.742	0.448	0.535	0.562	28
29.	Kalaburagi	0.726	0.420	0.514	0.539	29
30.	Yadgir	0.764	0.382	0.533	0.538	30
	Karnataka	0.759	0.555	0.634	0.644	

Source: Karnataka human Development Report 2022

Table no 5 show that the 2022 Human Development Report for Karnataka highlights that all districts in the state have improved their Human Development Index (HDI). The report's theme is "Bridging the Gaps towards Sustainable Well-being" Bengaluru urban stands highest in terms of Human development achievement at district level and will be categorised as

district with high human development as per UNDP international comparison. Followed by Dakshina Kannada, Chikkamagaluru, Udupi and Kodagu are the top 5 districts with higher human development achievements. Yadgir, Kalaburagi, Raichur, Haveri and Davanagere are the bottom 5 districts with low human development performance. It noted that the life expectancy in Karnataka has increased to 69.5 years while maternal mortality ratio has come down to 83 per lakh live births in 2022 to 69 in 2022.

Table 4: Trends of Human Development Index across the districts of Karnataka

Years		2011		2015		2022	
Sl. No	Districts	HDI index	Rank	HDI index	Rank	HDI index	Rank
1.	Bengaluru Urban	0.928	1	0.7392	1	0.738	1
2.	Dakshina Kannada	0.691	2	0.6636	3	0.687	2
3.	Chikkamagaluru	0.627	5	0.6360	5	0.668	3
4.	Udupi	0.675	3	0.6313	6	0.665	4
5.	Kodagu	0.658	4	0.6816	2	0.664	5
6.	Mandya	0.491	15	0.5986	14	0.644	6
7.	Bengaluru Rural	0.603	7	0.6484	4	0.643	7
8.	Ramanagar	0.533	13	0.5916	15	0.642	8
9.	Kolar	0.543	11	0.6266	7	0.640	9
10.	Shimoga	0.596	8	0.6101	10	0.636	10
11.	Uttara Kannada	0.565	10	0.6099	11	0.632	11
12.	Bagalkot	0.384	24	0.5513	24	0.629	12
13.	Chikkaballapur	0.486	16	0.6072	13	0.628	13
14.	Mysore	0.533	12	0.6204	9	0.625	14
15.	Hassan	0.576	9	0.6081	12	0.624	15
16.	Gadag	0.35	26	0.5715	20	0.623	16
17.	Tumkur	0.471	17	0.5807	17	0.615	17
18.	Bellary	0.354	25	0.5446	26	0.612	18
19.	Dharwad	0.61	6	0.6235	8	0.610	19
20.	Belgaum	0.296	18	0.5794	18	0.601	20
21.	Chamarajanager	0.234	22	0.5683	21	0.601	21
22.	Bidar	0.189	26	0.5651	22	0.600	22
23.	Vijayapura	0.33	27	0.5757	19	0.599	23
24.	Chitradurga	0.386	23	0.5597	23	0.597	24
25.	Koppal	0.28	28	0.5510	25	0.593	25
26.	Davangere	0.528	14	0.5827	16	0.589	26

27	Haveri	0.406	21	0.5390	28	0.566	27
28	Raichur	0.165	30	0.5399	27	0.562	28
29	Kalaburagi	0.407	20	0.5342	29	0.539	29
30	Yadgir	0.196	29	0.4954	30	0.538	30
Total Karnataka		0.508		0.611		0.644	

Source: UNDP, Karnataka Human Development Report-2022(Provisional).

Karnataka's first Human Development Report was published in 1999, focusing on regional imbalances in the state. The HDI has grown from 0.429 to 0.644 over 1990 to 2022 with an annual average growth of 1.42 per cent. Over the last two decades, the HDI of all the districts has improved significantly," the report says, adding that Karnataka is above the national HDI average of 45.9 per cent. Karnataka is in medium Human Development range (0.550-0.699) and rank is more or less stable between 10 & 11, but the index has improved significantly from 0.432 to 0.644. It implies that, the state's achievement in human development has increased from 43% to 64.4%. It is well above the national average in all the years. The above table provides the comparison of district wise HDI over two periods 2011, 2015 and 2022. All the districts witnessed an improvement in human development except Kodagu, Dharwad and Bengaluru Rural districts which shows marginal decline in HDI.

Comparing Human Development Index of 2011 and 2019 across the Mandya districts of Karnataka

Sl.No	Taluks	2011					2019				
		Health	Education	Standard of living	HDI	Rank	Health	Education	Standard of living	HDI	Rank
1.	<u>Krishnarajpet</u>	0.914	0.641	0.204	0.493	7	0.8106	0.4292	0.6032	0.5942	7
2.	<u>Maddur</u>	0.900	0.674	0.537	0.688	3	0.8273	0.5241	0.5996	0.6382	2
3.	<u>Malavalli</u>	0.850	0.428	0.430	0.539	6	0.8304	0.4391	0.6166	0.6081	5
4.	<u>Mandya</u>	0.441	1.000	0.754	0.693	2	0.8896	0.5447	0.7014	0.6979	1
5.	<u>Nagamangala</u>	0.953	0.480	0.391	0.563	5	0.8564	0.4142	0.5973	0.5961	6
6.	<u>Pandavapura</u>	0.850	0.596	0.484	0.626	4	0.8209	0.4832	0.6279	0.6292	3
7.	<u>Srirangapatna</u>	0.920	0.682	0.696	0.758	1	0.8275	0.4668	0.6064	0.6164	4

Source: Karnataka Human Development Report-2022(Provisional).

The above table shows the Human Development Index of different taluks of Mandya district in 2011 and 2019. Mandya district has a total of seven taluks and when comparing the human development index of seven taluks, it can be seen that there is a difference in them. Mandya taluk ranked first with HDI values of 0.6979 in the year 2019 among various taluks of Mandya district. And Krishnarajpet was ranked 7th with HDI values of 0.5942, Maddur was ranked 2nd with HDI values of 0.6382, Pandavapura was ranked 3rd with HDI values of 0.6292, Srirangapatna taluk was ranked 4th with HDI values of 0.6164, Malavalli was ranked 5th with HDI values of 0.6081, Nagamangala was ranked 3rd with HDI values of 0.5961. 6th position. If you look at the human development index of Mandya district, the human development index of people living in urban areas is higher as compared to the people of rural areas, because they have health, education and sources of income in a better condition compared to the people of rural areas. It can be observed that the human development index of all the taluks of Mandya district is better in 2019 as compared to 2011. Besides, it can be observed in the above list that there has been improvement in health education and quality of life.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H₁: There is statistically significant difference in Disparities in Human development index in across the taluks of Mandya District in Karnataka in 2019.									
	Observed Frequencies in 2019				Expected Frequencies				
Taluks	Health	Education	Standard of living	HDI	Health	Education	Standard of living	HDI	Total
<u>Krishnarajpet</u>	0.8106	0.4292	0.6032	0.5942	0.7984	0.4496	0.5927	0.5965	2.4372
<u>Maddur</u>	0.8273	0.5241	0.5996	0.6382	0.8482	0.4776	0.6297	0.6337	2.5892
<u>Malavalli</u>	0.8304	0.4391	0.6166	0.6081	0.8171	0.4601	0.6066	0.6104	2.4942
<u>Mandya</u>	0.8896	0.5447	0.7014	0.6979	0.9283	0.5227	0.6891	0.6935	2.8336
<u>Nagamangala</u>	0.8564	0.4142	0.5973	0.5961	0.8072	0.4545	0.5992	0.6031	2.464
<u>Pandavapura</u>	0.8209	0.4832	0.6279	0.6292	0.839	0.4725	0.6229	0.6268	2.5612
<u>Srirangapatna</u>	0.8275	0.4668	0.6064	0.6164	0.8246	0.4643	0.6122	0.6161	2.5171
Total					5.8627	3.3013	4.3524	4.3801	17.897
Compute Chi-square	$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}}$								
Compute the degrees of freedom (df).	Compute the degrees of freedom (df). $df = (4-1) \cdot (7-1) = 18$								
p-value	for 18 df, $p(\chi^2 \geq 0.0194) = 0$								
Hypothesis testing result	Since the p-value (0) < α (0.01) (two-tailed test), we reject the null hypothesis H ₀								

CONCLUSION

The Human Development Index (HDI) measures each country's social and economic development by focusing on the following four factors: mean years of schooling, expected years of schooling, life expectancy at birth, and gross national income (GNI) per capita. The HDI is an essential tool for measuring a nation's overall growth, taking into account key socio-economic factors. It provides a comprehensive overview of a country's performance in these areas. The HDI ranks countries on the Human Development Scale in terms of the abilities of humans within countries to perform tasks. However, the HDI provides a limited evaluation of human development. It does not specifically reflect quality of life factors, such as empowerment movements or overall feelings of security. The HDI has grown from 0.429 to 0.644 over 1990 to 2022 with an annual average growth of 1.42 per cent. Over the last two decades, the HDI of all the districts has improved significantly," in Karnataka. It noted that the life expectancy in Karnataka has increased to 69.5 years while maternal mortality ratio has come down to 83 per lakh live births in 2022 to 69 in 2022. This study shows that Mandya district in Karnataka has a Human Development Index (HDI) of 0.644 in 2022-23. The HDI is a summary of a country's average achievements in three basic aspects of human development: health, knowledge, and standard of living. Mandya district has a total of seven taluks and when comparing the human development index of seven taluks, it can be seen that there is a difference in them. Mandya taluk ranked first with HDI values of 0.6979 in the year 2019 among various taluks of Mandya district. And Krishnarajpet was ranked 7th with HDI values of 0.5942, Maddur was ranked 2nd with HDI values of 0.6382, Pandavapura was ranked 3rd with HDI values of 0.6292, Srirangapatna taluk was ranked 4th with HDI values of 0.6164, Malavalli was ranked 5th with HDI values of 0.6081, Nagamangala was

ranked 3rd with HDI values of 0.5961. 6th position. If you look at the human development index of Mandya district, the human development index of people living in urban areas is higher as compared to the people of rural areas, because they have health, education and sources of income in a better condition compared to the people of rural areas. It can be observed that the human development index of all the taluks of Mandya district is better in 2019 as compared to 2011. Besides, it can be observed in the above list that there has been improvement in health education and quality of life.

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